

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Available online

<http://www.arseam.com>

Email us: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS (PPP'S) - A FUTURE INVENTION OF DEVELOPMENTS

Rupak Karmakar

Guest Lecturer, Department of commerce,
Barasat College., Barasat, P:o- Nabapally, Kolkata, India.

Abstract

This study showed that how private sector provides services on behalf of the govt. PPP's can mobilize additional sources of funding's & financial infrastructure In recent years it is an essential part of market structure & maintenance of asset quality in better manner.in that global crisis govt. are not enough fund for infrastructure development so PPP's can offer the essential source of fund to make the govt. a stronger part of the society.

KEYWORDS: - Electric power, Waste disposal, Clean Water, Sanitation, Model school.

Introduction:-

A public-private partnership (PPP) is an agreement between the government & private sector for the purpose of provisioning of public services or infrastructure. The govt. of India has been flourishing on the development of enabling tools & activities to encourage private sector investment in the country through the PPP format. In 1970's & 1980's govt. sought to encourage private investment in infrastructure ; initially on the basis of accounting fallacies arising from the fact that public accounts did not distinguish between recurrent & capital expenditures. Private investments amounting to us \$150 billion is expected to bridge the infrastructure gap of us \$500 billion over the period 2007-2012. The Govt. of India plays a very significant role by PPP for increasing the quality of economic & infrastructure facility compare to recent past. Govt. is attracted to PPP's because they may provide value for money – at least in the short term. A key challenge facing governments around the world is the need to provide better services in transport, electric, power, waste disposal, clean water & sanitation health & education among all, so govt. not yet sufficient fund to organize those kind of facilities so another reason to adopt public-private partnership in an essential manner.

Objectives:-

Public-private partnerships are the following objectives, such as:-

Contribution to sustainable developments-

Public-private partnership (PPP's) mobilizes private sector resources technical, managerial & financial to deliver essential public services such as infrastructure, health & education. Such development we mainly divided into two parts which are-

- a) Economic infrastructure.
- b) Social infrastructure.

Economic infrastructure-

Infrastructure forms the backbone of a nation with the noble aim of funding the most commercially viable infrastructure projects to extend access of roads, safe drinking water, electricity, sanitation & other basic amenities to the people in mass in India. Governments are attracted to PPP's because they may provide value for money- at least in the short term. The ability to transfer risk to whichever of the public or private partner is better able to manage the risk is a source of value for money significant growth in the number of PPP's in the 15 years has made India one of the leading PPP markets in world. As a result a proper PPP eco-system comprising institution, developers, financiers', equity providers, policies & procedure has emerged.

- PPP in Highway-

With an extensive road network India is the second largest in the world. Indian roads carry about 61% of the freight & 85% of the passenger traffic. Indian govt. annually spends about RS. 18000 cores (USD 3.704 billion).

- **Future targets-**
 - i) Developing 1000km of express ways.
 - ii) Developing 8737km of roads, including 3846km of national highways in the north east.
 - iii) Four lanning 20000km of national highways.
 - iv) Four lanning 6736km on north-south & east-west corridors.
 - v) Six lanning 6500km of the Golden quadrilateral selected national highways.
 - vi) Widening 20000km of national highways to two lanes.

Since January 2006 the public-private partnership appraisal committee (PPPAC) has granted approval to a total of 87 projects including 77 highway projects. The PPPAC approves the infrastructure projects worth US \$ 5.98 billion on November 2008.

- PPP in Power-

The total installed capacity in India is calculated to be 145554.97 megawatt, out of which 75837.93 megawatt (52.5%) is from state, 48470.99 megawatt (34%) is from central & 21246.05 megawatt (13.5%) is from private sector initiatives. Majority of generation, transmission & distribution capacities are with either public sector companies or with State Electricity Boards (SEBs), private sector such as NTPC, National Hydro Electric Power Corporation, Nuclear Power Corporation, Tata Power, RPG group, Reliance Energy etc. participation is increasing day by day especially by in generation & distribution.

- PPP in Railways-

Indian railway is the backbone of the socio economic growth in India. The Indian railway has initiated one of the most challenging growth targets for the coming year involving with PPP models. Such initiatives are-

- i) Development of PPP envisaged in need routes, railway station, logistic parks, cargo aggregation & warehouses.
- ii) Developments of 100 budget hotels with private participation in the vicinity of railway stations etc.

Social infrastructure:-

Not only economic infrastructure public-private partnership (PPP's) is becoming a common tool to bring together the strength of both sectors such as economic & social infrastructure. The central govt. is working with the state govt. to expand the horizon of PPP in social infrastructure development in the country. Social infrastructure such as schools, hospitals, libraries etc. considered essential for the structure of society. In India many parts are rural side, we believe that India's challenge in building up the rural infrastructure that is so vital. Building up a strong rural infrastructure will undoubtedly provide a much needed impetus to economic growth PPP's are the main ingredient of this infrastructure tools.

○ PPP's in school-

The implementation of the right to Education Act, India is poised to provide quality education to all children in the country. The rapid changes witnessed in technological world & the general need to improve the quality of life & to reduce poverty, it is essential that school's leavers acquire a higher level of knowledge & skills. At present some schemes targeted at secondary stage such as,

- i) Rashtriya Madhyamik Siksha Abhiyan (RMSA)
- ii) Model school Scheme.
- iii) Girls Hostels Scheme
- iv) ICT @ School
- v) Scheme of Vocational Education
- vi) National Means – Cum Merit Scholarships Scheme etc.

Under Model school scheme 2500 model schools are setting up under Public-private Partnership (PPP's) mode. A model school will have infrastructure & facilities at least of the same standard as in a Kendriya Vidyalaya (KV) & with stipulations on pupil teacher's ratio, ICT usage, Holistic educational environment, appropriate curriculum & emphasis on output & outcome.

Some of the key features of a model school will be-

- i) Education provided in a model school should be holistic & integral touching upon physical, emotional & aesthetic developments in addition to academics.
- ii) Necessary infrastructure will be provided in such school not only for satisfying teaching needs, but also for sports & co-curricular activities. There will be sufficient scope for sports, recreation & outdoor activities facilities like playground gardens; auditorium etc. will be provided in model schools. A good library with books & magazines for students & teachers will be provided.
- iii) These schools will have adequate ICT infrastructure internet connectivity & full time computer teachers. Specials emphasis may be given on teaching of science, math's & English. If required bridge courses may be introduced for weak students.
- iv) These schools will be provided with arts & music teachers besides subject specific teachers as per the usual norms. These schools will also create facility for activities emphasizing Indian heritage & art & craft etc.

○ PPP's in Hospitals-

Public-private partnership or PPP in the context of the health sector is an instrument for improving the health of the population. PPP is to be seen in the context of viewing the whole medical sector as a national asset with health promotion as goal of all health providers, private or public. Some health schemes which are successfully in PPP models in India which are –

- i) Yeshasvini Health Scheme in Karnataka- The yeshavini co-operative farmer's health-care scheme is a health insurance scheme targeted to benefit the poor. It was initiated by Narayana Hrudayalaya, super specialty heart hospital in Bangalore & by the department of co-operatives of the governments of Karnataka. Such card holders could access free treatment in 160 hospitals located in all district of the state for any medical procedure costing up to RS. 2 lakh.

- ii) Arogya Raksha Scheme in Andhra Pradesh- The govt. of Andhra Pradesh has initiated the Arogya Raksha Scheme in collaboration with the New India Assurance Company & with private clinics. It is an insurance scheme fully funded by the govt. It provides hospitalization benefits & personal accident benefits to citizens below the poverty line who undergo sterilization for family planning from govt. health institutions.
- iii) Telemedicine initiative by Narayana Hrudayalaya in Karnataka- The govt. of Karnataka , the Narayana Hrudayalaya hospital in Bangalore & its India space Research organization initiated an experimental Tele-medicine project called Karnataka integrated Tele-medicine & Tele- health Project (KITTH) which is an on line health care initiatives in Karnataka.

Such kind of health facilities will give better quality of life in future aspect.

Conclusion:-

The recent global economic & financial crisis has generated challenges at all levels of economic policy decisions. The central govt. also state govt. & private sector are mostly suffering for this economic challenge. This study showed that public-private partnerships (PPP's) are vulnerable to both the financial & the real impact of the crisis. PPP programs could affect in various field, such as lower growth, social infrastructure. It has been witnessed that public-private partnership format with its mixed success across the global, has been acknowledge as an essential tool for focused private sector investment in economic & social infrastructure projects. Despite many challenges Indian PPP has been successful in many sectors which we discuss earlier. We hopefully that in next phase PPP's are more successful in infrastructure developments in recent years.

Reference:-

- i) Institute for international cooperation (IFIC) & Japan international corporation agency (JICA) - progress with public private partnership projects in Developing countries(draft)
- ii) Department of the parliamentary library (200-03) - public private partnerships: An introduction.
- iii) Philippe Burger, Justin Tyson, Izbela karpowicz, & Maria Delgado (2009) - The effects of the Financial Crisis on public private partnerships.
- iv) Johannes Justing (1999) - public private partnership & social protection in developing countries: the case of health sector.
- v) FICCI (ERNST & YOUNG) - Accelerating public private partnership in India.
- vi) Partnership British Colombia (2003) - An Introduction to public partnerships.
- vii) M. Sathana.Priya & p. Jesintha (2011) - public private partnership in India.
- viii) Manish Luthra & shikha mahajan- Role of public partnership in school Education in India.
- ix) UNECE – Introduction to public-private partnerships.
- x) Department of PPP in India.
- xi) The World Bank Institute – Focus on public-private partnerships.
- xii) Govt. of India, Ministry of Finance, Approach paper on defining public private partnerships.
- xiii) L. Lakshmanan (2008) – public private partnership in Indian infrastructure developments: issue & options.
- xiv) Karthik Murlidharan – public private partnerships for quality education in India.
- xv) KPMG - public private partnerships in India.
- xvi) TCA Anant & Ram Singh – distribution of Highway public private partnerships in India: key legal & economic determinants.
- xvii) Department of School Education & Literacy, Ministry of Human Resources Developments, Govt. of India.
- xviii) Wikipedia.